

ISW

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Author	Karol Zając, Jan Meizner, Taras Zhyhulin, Piotr Nowakowski
Contributors	Sano, UNIBO

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List of abbreviations

ISW	In Silico World
WP	Work Package
HPC	High Performance Computing
MEE	Model Execution Environment
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
API	Application Programming Interface
DMT	Deep Modelling Track
DAT	Deep Accreditation Track
ATMP	Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products
FAME	Fractional flow reserve versus Angiography for Multivessel Evaluation trial
FEM	Finite Element Method

1. Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a summary of scalability strategies adopted for the ISW project, including the deployment of tools such as the Model Execution Environment (MEE) [1] to manage the wide range of available resources and results of those actions.

Over the course of the project, Work Package 6 maintained interaction with developers of ISW computational models to enable these models to be executed on large-scale computing resources available to the consortium and to do so in an efficient and organized manner using a toolkit – based on the Model Execution Environment – which was further extended with additional features and integrated with external components of the ISW computational framework. Following this stage, WP6 coordinated large-scale production runs of ISW models, an activity which is ongoing as of the publication date of this deliverable, and which is expected to continue throughout the remainder of the project, and beyond.

The deliverable reports on the development work which took place in the context of WP6, and provides a summary of the status of integration of ISW computational models with the available computing infrastructure. Results of ongoing studies are also described.

2. Description of computational tools and resources

2.1 Hardware services

The hardware used for the processing of the ISW models is composed of the following components:

- The Model Execution Environment requires no hardware as it is deployed in the Software as a Service model by the Polish grid infrastructure PLGrid [2] as described in detail later in this document
- Persistent services maintained by Sano, such as the monitoring platform, are deployed on Sano's own hardware co-located in the professional Data Center, meeting the highest standard of availability (UPSes, emergency power generators with redundancy) and security (on-site 24/7 security, cameras, electronic locks, multiple security zones). A detailed description of the server infrastructures is provided later in this section. Those servers are also available for initial preprocessing of data as needed.
- Regular computations are run via the MEE platform on the HPC infrastructure provided as part of the PLGrid grant, which provides infrastructure for Polish scientists and their

international collaborators on the free basis. The sole requirement for scientists is to produce valid results such as conference or journal papers and appropriately attribute the PLGrid infrastructure. Currently, Sano is utilizing the grant consisting of 2,000,000 core hours and 1 TB of storage, which provide sample resources for this phase of the ISW project. When needed, grants may be renegotiated (expanded), or new grants may be negotiated to enable continuation of the work.

The aforementioned local Sano mini-cluster for the persistent services is composed of:

- Single management node with the Intel Xeon E-2234 CPU and 32 GB of RAM
- 2 GPU-accelerated compute nodes (NVIDIA QUADRO RTX A4000 with 16 GB GPU memory each), with dual Intel Xeon Silver 4214R CPUs (12 cores / 24 threads each) enabling execution of 48 threads in parallel, 128 GB of RAM per node and 960 GB of local high-performance SSD storage in RAID10 configuration per node. Each server is also equipped with a fast dual 10 Gbps interconnect, in addition to 1 Gbps management network (2 + 1 dedicated to out-of-band management).
- Appropriate network switches to provide connectivity between the nodes

2.2 Software services

2.2.1 Model Execution Environment

The main tool allowing the seamless execution of ISW solutions is the Model Execution Environment (MEE). It is a web application for managing patient-oriented workflows [Figure 1] and its execution. MEE was created by Cyfronet [3] and is used within many projects as the engine for running various experiments on Polish HPC infrastructure.

From the beginning of the ISW project, MEE was developed according to the following principles [4]:

- Model versioning
- 3R rule – Repeatability, Replicability, Reproducibility

Main MEE functionality offers:

- Research separation – organizations (groups) membership
- Reproducibility, versioning, and documentation of the pipeline
- Automation of the simulation pipeline with humans in the loop for:
 - new models, new versions of models
 - new users
- Data preservation
- Basic provenance features
- Helpful visualization of simulation flow and obtained results

Sano uses this environment to provide easy access to simulation experiments and workflow control. However, in terms of Task 6.2 “Ensuring scalability and efficiency of the large-scale simulations” new features have been implemented to facilitate model execution at scale and to enhance its presentation layer. The following features and implementations have been developed and introduced in a number of new MEE releases during M13-M42 of the ISW project.

Figure 1: Model Execution Environment workflow structure diagram.

Cohorts

To enhance the scalability of pipeline execution on patients, cohorts have been introduced in MEE. Cohorts facilitate the creation of patient sets by adding existing patients to them.

To simplify the usage of cohorts, mass patient upload was introduced in MEE [Figure 2]. It enables cohorts to be populated with patients from a specially constructed zip file containing their data. Such a tool can be utilized in large-scale simulations to expedite the process of providing necessary data to the model and sharing it among research team members.

Figure 2: Cohort view with patient management and mass patient upload zone

Campaigns

So far, the Model Execution Environment has allowed to run a single workflow configuration for a specific patient. The concept of campaigns [Figure 3] has been implemented to conduct simulations on patient cohorts. They allow for the creation of pipelines following a specific flow for a particular patients and aggregating them into a campaign. Such a campaign can be executed automatically in a cohort, performing computations for each patient in the set.

Figure 3: Cohort-Campaign relationship. Campaign execution view.

During the execution of the campaign, the progress of computations can be monitored by tracking their statuses. The aggregated progress of the campaign is presented in a progress bar containing information about the number of successfully finished, still running, or failed pipelines. The results of every computation performed during campaign execution are presented in a table and segregated based on patients from the cohort.

Storage

S3 storage has been integrated with MEE, thus enabling the connection of a specific bucket to an organization and the storage of the data for each workflow in the S3 cloud.

Integration with data repositories

Integration with data repositories such as Dataverse [5] and Zenodo [6] has been implemented to introduce enhanced data sharing and management capabilities. This integration enables the downloading and uploading of data to a connected data repository during workflow execution. Specifically, a Dataverse instance has been deployed to store data for research teams.

2.2.2 Dataverse instance

The Sano Dataverse instance has been introduced to support data management within the project and to handle large amounts of simulation data produced in the future. Dataverse instance allows us to browse, share, and manage published or draft data on secure S3 storage. Thanks to the integration with MEE, users can easily access the required data input from an external Dataverse instance and

Figure 4: Storage usage for MEE organization's data.

fetch them directly to the job execution directory. The access is based on API tokens that can be set up to utilize the instance API and securely download/upload data.

The above implementations contributed to the MS6.1 (M36) “Infrastructure for secure data management ready” milestone accomplishment. More detailed descriptions will be included along with the D6.4 (M48) “Open Source software for rule-based data sharing” deliverable, which will sum up WP6 work on data management and sharing.

3. Integration, deployment, and execution of ISW computational models

In this section, we report in detail the progress of the integration of the ISW computational models within the WP6 infrastructure, focusing not only on the deployment but also on the execution and the experiments conducted with these models. This process has been marked by several key activities, ensuring a seamless and efficient implementation of computational models within our infrastructure.

The adaptation, deployment, and execution of the in silico models have been critical components of the scalability and efficiency strategy. WP6 efforts have been guided by a commitment to continuous improvement and responsiveness to the evolving needs of the WP2 teams which worked on model development.

To provide continuous updates and model versioning, a dynamic update mechanism for the ISW models has been established, with new versions being uploaded to specific GitLab [7] repositories [Figure 5] on an ongoing basis. This ensures that the latest enhancements and all versions of the model are readily available and usable as an MEE workflow for all users.

Figure 5: GitLab group with collected models integrated with Model Execution Environment.

Each repository includes workflow steps scripts that describe configurable pipelines for execution. In response to specific model experiments and workflows, Sano has configured multiple on-demand versions of pipelines. These configurations are aligned with the requirements analysis outlined in D6.1 deliverable, allowing us to meet diverse research and operational needs effectively.

The infrastructure has seen an influx of new users from the ISW partners after conducting workshops or demonstratory presentations of MEE and its integrations. This growing user base reflects the expanding utilization of developed solutions in WP6. Thus, Sano continues to provide robust support

for these new users, facilitating smooth onboarding and integration into our systems. The newly created organizations in the Model Execution Environment for various ISW use cases are actively managed by MEE administrators who serve their assistance, which includes workflow execution, monitoring of large-scale production runs, and troubleshooting. This comprehensive management ensures that the ISW models operate efficiently and reliably within the infrastructure provided for the project.

Furthermore, integrated solutions have enabled WP6 to test newly implemented MEE features, such as cohorts-campaigns, on real project use cases. This practical testing is essential for validating the functionality and performance of these features, ensuring they meet the high standards required in the HPC environment.

WP6 ongoing efforts in these areas highlight the dedication to integrate, deploy, and execute ISW computational models in a manner that maximizes efficiency, reliability, and scalability. Through continuous updates, configurable pipelines, user support, robust management, and experiment monitoring, we are advancing the capabilities and impact of the ISW project.

3.1 BoneStrength

Digital Twin for femur fracture risk biomarker. In Silico Trial for osteoporosis drugs.

BoneStrength follows a highly important approach called Digital Twin, which represents an in silico model of a real-world object: in this case, a femur bone. The model utilizes Finite Element Method (FEM) based simulations backed by the ANSYS [8] Mechanical suite to simulate bone load during specific patient fall conditions, in order to predict its possible fracture.

Two approaches to BoneStrength were developed: the Standard version and the Markov version, both wrapped into a workflow available for usage on the Model Execution Environment [Figure 6]. The initial integration was completed and presented at the MEE workshop organized by Sano. The Standard version was adapted to align with a patient-oriented concept, allowing a single patient to be simulated multiple times by running different pipelines with various parameters. Conversely, the Markov version was designed to facilitate the simulation of multiple patients under various fall conditions through a single pipeline.

Figure 6: Workflow step for simulating Markov version of BoneStrength.

For a single simulation of one fall condition, supported by Intel MPI, the following resources are required: 4 CPUs, at least 8 GB memory, up to 5 GB disk space for the ANSYS software working directory. These resource requirements are essential for the baseline execution of the simulation.

However, the amount of RAM and job time limit can be adjusted as pipeline parameters to accommodate more complex simulations characterized by lower convergence rates and varied ANSYS solver processing. This flexibility allows us to process and simulate the realization campaigns efficiently and, if needed, rerun more demanding cases with increased allocation of resources. Processing one specific case takes mostly from 10 to 20 minutes when using the mentioned allocation.

The most computationally expensive experiments are the BoneStrength In Silico Trials, which are a practical use case to estimate the risk of bone fracture within a set of patients (called a cohort) in the form of a campaign simulation. The single campaign realization simulates thousands of generated falls which are randomly assigned to the cohort's patients along a certain observation time.

This type of experiment uses a constructed workflow that submits to the HPC cluster an array job whose size is determined by the number of cases to be processed in a campaign. Due to limitations in the number of ANSYS software licenses available on the UNIBO server, the number of simulations that run simultaneously can be adjusted by a parameter specified during the pipeline setup in the MEE. This ensures that the license server is not overused, and on the other hand users can submit larger campaigns.

Several cohorts (thousands of virtual patients) were uploaded to the Ares cluster, which is being used by partners from UNIBO to conduct the in silico trials and sensitivity analysis mentioned above. Users can submit campaigns from MEE by uploading .csv files with campaign records (patient id, fall conditions) and providing a path to the cohort data on Ares storage.

Figure 7: Campaign realizations submitted from Model Execution Environment.

The BoneStrength team has successfully simulated multiple campaign realizations across various patient cohorts with differing specifications. These extensive experiments encompassed approximately 300,000 simulated BoneStrength cases. The execution of these simulations was significantly accelerated and made feasible through the solutions provided, demonstrating the effectiveness and scalability of our infrastructure.

We have successfully deployed multiple versions [Figure 8] of workflows using MEE, allowing us to satisfy diverse experimental requirements and maintain flexibility in model execution.

Figure 8: Model versions of BoneStrength available on MEE.

The BoneStrength campaign initiative inspired the development and implementation of a new Campaign/Cohort mechanism in MEE (described in the Software Services section). This mechanism enables the execution of a single workflow for multiple patients simultaneously, greatly enhancing efficiency and throughput in processing patient-specific simulations. The MEE campaign version can substitute the array tasks version in the scenario where the same set of fall conditions have to be simulated for each patient. Additionally, instead of using Ares cluster storage, the MEE storage can be used to store patients uploaded from zip files along with their input data required for simulation. Bulk patient uploads for a cohort allows for convenient patient browsing and data file management.

3.2 AngioSupport

In Silico Trial and clinical decision support tool for myocardial infarction.

AngioSupport is a DMT application to be used both as a clinical decision support system and In Silico Trial tool for myocardial infarction. The 1D model is implemented using Python and 3D model uses ANSYS Fluent through the PyFluent [9] Python library.

The AngioSupport model is continuously being updated, and multiple versions are anticipated. These versions are managed using MEE model versioning, enabling users to select the appropriate model version when initiating simulations on the platform. Currently, the complete 1D model has been adapted, which is running on default SLURM [10] allocation since it uses a single core and does not require a significant amount of memory. The execution time depends on the version of the model since the implementation of AngioSupport is greatly parametrized inside the model class, which can optionally use the preprocessing operations on geometries or postprocessing operations, still being changed during model development. The workflow generates multiple .vtu and .mat data files containing pressures, resistances, and other relevant metrics. Additionally, it produces a 3D plot of segmented angio geometry, which can be displayed within the MEE.

Figure 9: AngioSupport outputs in Model Execution Environment.

To facilitate user-specific requirements, the model utilizes a configuration file that allows users to override global parameters based on their experimental needs and use cases. This flexibility ensures that the model can be tailored to various scenarios, thus enhancing its applicability and utility at the current state of its development.

Besides single model execution, WP6 enabled the possibility to execute a sensitivity analysis (SA) pipeline that has been introduced to run the 1D model multiple times with varying sample parameters. Such an experiment required an optimization of the delivered SA model to be able to process all samples in a reasonable time. SA pipeline for AngioSupport consists of a two-step [Figure 10] process:

1. Execution of the 1D Model Using Array Jobs

The first step involves running the 1D model using an array job that submits tasks to the HPC cluster. Each task processes a subset of samples, distributing the workload evenly since the model execution time is almost consistent across samples. This parallel processing significantly reduces the total computation time compared to sequential execution.

2. Aggregation and Error Handling

The results from each task are saved into a .mat file with variables corresponding to specific sample IDs. When all workers generate results, a second step is automatically invoked to concatenate these individual outputs into a single .mat file. This step also verifies and collects error samples that the model could not process, along with error messages.

Figure 10: Sensitivity Analysis workflow execution for AngioSupport 1D model.

Figure 11: Sensitivity Analysis step parametrization on MEE.

Since the AngioSupport model reads patient data from the local FAME datafile, the PatientID can be passed as a pipeline parameter. AngioSupport SA returns the values at the specific points of the patient’s angio segments, which can be changed by passing the list of node IDs where the measurement should be done. Depending on the scale of the experiment, the number of parallel workers and their time limits can be specified as additional arguments.

The SA pipeline has been tested on the first patients using 5000 input samples distributed across 250 workers. The usage of the optimized workflow allowed the SA experiment to run 140 times faster compared to the original sequential sample processing.

3.3 VirtualFD

Flow diverters for cerebral aneurysms.

VirtualFD is a solution for the evaluation of the influence of flow diverters on blood flow. It is based on Palabos, an open-source parallel Lattice-Boltzmann solver written in C++ with MPI parallelization, already deployed in various HPC centres in Europe.

Models are created, and results are elaborated graphically by an operator, while simulations are run in batch mode. Each simulation requires 8 CPU cores (30-50 core hours total), 8-16 GB of RAM, and generates 100-200 result files, occupying 20-40 GB. In order to have a meaningful output, 2500-5000 simulations are needed.

Similarly to BoneStrength, a medium- to high-level workstation is enough for the computational requirements of a single simulation run, but a large number of simulations requires a computing cluster.

The MEE pipeline has been constructed to facilitate the efficient execution of the VirtualFD model using the executable and .xml patient input files. During the porting of the model to the Ares cluster, a crucial step was the preparation of the executable by configuring specific Ares module dependencies with CMake and OpenMPI. This initial step ensures the executable is ready for model execution. The actual execution pipeline leverages the generated executable from the ISW storage group and requires a .xml patient input file. Additionally, the number of CPU cores used for MPI can be adjusted to optimize performance.

WP6, in collaboration with the VirtualFD team, plans to conduct the first large-scale experiment, which will include approximately 500 CFD simulations for 30 patients. The currently developed MEE tools are fully capable of handling this scale. They allow the efficient upload of patient data and their

corresponding simulation inputs, and MEE campaign mechanism enables to run the VirtualFD model multiple times for all patients.

3.4 UISS-TB, UISS-COVID19, UISS-MS, UISS-MC

In Silico Trial for tuberculosis vaccine. Vaccines and therapies for COVID-19. In Silico Trial for multiple sclerosis drugs. Immunotherapies for mammary carcinoma.

UISS is an immune system simulator developed in different flavours targeting various diseases, namely: tuberculosis, Covid-19, multiple sclerosis, mammary carcinoma. The simulation pattern is a replica computing of an agent-based model (ABM) written in ANSI C where the simulations are performed in batch mode.

Each simulation runs on 1 CPU core for about 10 minutes and requires at least 4 GB of RAM and 10 MB of free disk space. A typical use case involves 100 patients, each with 30 replicas (to account for ABM stochasticity), for a total of 3000 simulations.

Single ABM simulations are not very demanding; the need for a compute cluster arises due to the number of simulations to be run or the urgency of the use scenario.

Three UISS solutions (UISS-TB, UISS-COVID19, UISS-MS) have been successfully integrated with our infrastructure and configured on the MEE [Figure 12]. While the UISS-MC solution has not yet been delivered, its adaptation will follow the established mechanisms used for other UISS framework solutions.

Figure 12: Adaptation process of UISS applications and results in MEE UI.

Applications are running as Singularity containers. The executable file is launched by running a Singularity image file with the exec command and passing UISS datafile as required input. The workflow has been deployed on MEE and streamlined into three steps:

- Initialization – Pulling the docker image from the repository and, based on it, preparing SIF (Singularity Image File) on our \$SCRATCH. The converted SIF file can be cached.

- Simulation – Running UISS executable file with Singularity. Datafile is required as input to start executing. Generating and staging out result files describing immune system dynamics.
- (Optional) Analysis – Postprocessing of the results, which uses the Gnuplot module to generate plots.

Since the UISS framework developed by UNICT partners is being upgraded to a multithreaded version, Sano is going to test its possibilities with 48-core CPUs available on Ares cluster partitions.

3.5 OcDefects

ATMP for cartilage and bone tissues.

The OcDefects solution targets Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products (ATMP) for cartilage and bone tissues. It is a multiscale model (intracellular and tissue/organ scale) based on Abaqus (FE solver) and Matlab commercial software.

Model definition of FE models is done graphically, but simulations are run in batch mode. The production run of Monte Carlo simulations of intracellular models in Matlab is run in batch mode. A single-core execution of the multiscale model requires 16 GB of RAM, creates about 2 GB of files (1-2 GB for the FE tissue/joint model, 500 MB for the FE cellular model, < 500 KB for intracellular model), and requires about 8 hours (4 hours, 30 minutes, and 3 hours [first iteration] or 15 minutes [successive iterations], respectively). This time includes the generation of perturbations and attractors, which are the inputs required for the actual workflow.

The OcDefects multiscale model, adapted to MEE, comprises two parametrized pipeline steps [Figure 13]:

- Global Model Generation

The first step involves generating the global model using Abaqus, based on the input file. This step is essential for simulating individual cells and typically takes approximately one hour.

- Cell Simulation Array Job

The second step is an array job where each task simulates a specific cell using Abaqus. Each task requires a cell input file and properties describing the cell position. The output from this step is a cell model that determines the maximum integrin force, which is then used as an input for the intracellular model. This intracellular model is processed using Matlab. Running the cell model on 4 CPUs and subsequently processing the intracellular part with a single core takes several minutes.

Figure 13: OcDefects multiscale workflow steps.

Currently, the workflow for the OcDefects model is being enhanced with additional cell biological variables. Once this enhancement is complete, the OcDefects team will conduct their first experiment, which requires HPC power since it will simulate a single multiscale workflow for hundreds of cells [Figure 14] in parallel. Additionally, an analysis step that aggregates all the results

Figure 14: OcDefects MEE workflow diagram.

from the simulated cells can be added to the workflow in response to user requests. In the future, a constructed workflow can be executed for multiple patient/study cases.

3.6 InSole, ForceLoss, NeoIntima3D

While many of WP2's solutions were successfully deployed on our HPC infrastructure, some were not integrated due to specific requirements or developmental stages. Below, we discuss three such solutions - InSole, ForceLoss, and NeoIntima3D, highlighting their functionalities, resource requirements, and reasons for not being deployed on our HPC systems.

InSole

Personalised insole design.

InSole is a DAT solution based on OpenSim (open source software for musculoskeletal multibody modelling) simulations run through Python and Matlab (commercial software) API scripts.

Each subject requires 300 trial simulations, each requiring 10 minutes for initial condition definition, 4 hours for parameter optimization (OpenSim is repeatedly called to solve the model, as parameters

are varied by Matlab routines), and 10 minutes for final simulation with the obtained optimal parameters. The RAM consumption and disk space required for each trial optimization are modest (5-7 GB and 75 MB, respectively).

The primary reason for not integrating InSole into our HPC infrastructure is its current reliance on GUI interactions within the workflow, which complicates automated execution. While future plans include removing the need for a GUI to allow scalability and HPC utilization, the InSole team is currently not focusing on this aspect. Instead, they are simplifying the solution and possibly preparing for future sensitivity analyses that would benefit from HPC resources.

ForceLoss

Drugs for osteopenia.

ForceLoss is a DMT application for the differential diagnosis and treatment of sarcopenia. Like InSole, it is based on OpenSim simulations run by Python and Matlab APIs.

Due to the ongoing development phase, the primary focus has been on model implementation rather than on integration with WP6 systems. WP6 provided tools that may help in the future construction of scientific workflows using ForceLoss source codes or executables. Currently, without these critical components, it is not possible to evaluate its resource needs or optimize it for our systems.

NeoIntima3D

Evaluation for risk of thrombosis with drug-eluting stents.

NeoIntima3D is still in the early stages of development and has proven more complex than initially expected. It requires COMSOL software and its Finite Element (FE) solver for simulations, indicating substantial computational demands in the future.

The early development stage of NeoIntima3D means that significant additional effort would be required to adapt it to our infrastructure. At this point, the complexity and early stage of development make integration impractical. Preparing our cluster for the use of COMSOL software is noted for future consideration, but the solution is currently not ready for deployment on our HPC system.

3.7 WP6 workshops

As the WP6 leader, Sano organized two consortium-wide workshops to train ISW members on utilizing the provided services. In the first place, a Model Execution Environment tutorial has been prepared to present the possibilities of running computational models on HPC infrastructure. Real use cases from WP2 were available for workshop participants to familiarize themselves with system access and simulation execution during hands-on training.

Assuming that interested users already have basic knowledge, the next workshop, showing integrations with the MEE platform, has been conducted to even more facilitate the usage of advanced workflows and improve their scalability. Users could learn about new MEE features for seamless utilization of data collections from external data repositories, as well as how to enable monitoring systems to keep track of running experiments.

4. Conclusion and future work

Throughout the remainder of the project, our intent is to continue supporting the ISW application workflows, which entails supervision of large-scale production runs, with a view towards publications and presentation of the outcomes of this work at scientific conferences. While the work on adding additional features and integration options to the Model Execution Environment is largely complete, we will also continue to supervise and take care of the administration of this environment and troubleshoot any emerging issues arising in the context of ISW workflows. The outcome of work taking place in WP6 on the integration of data and model repositories, as well as on ensuring that workflows are executed in an optimized and monitored manner on the available computational resources, will be further summarized in two upcoming deliverables – D6.3 and D6.4, respectively –, both of which are due in the final month of the project.

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